

1 **Title** Surprising Eutectics: enhanced properties of ZnO-ZnWO₄ from visible to MIR

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17 **Keywords:** Metamaterial, eutectic, optical luminescence, second harmonic generation, ZnO,
18 ZnWO₄.

19
20 ZnO-ZnWO₄ is a self-organised eutectic composite consisting of parallel ZnO thin layers
21 (lamellae) embedded in a dielectric ZnWO₄ matrix. Electromagnetic behavior of composite
22 materials is affected not only by the properties of single constituent materials, but also by
23 their reciprocal geometrical micro-/nano-structurization, as in the case of ZnO-ZnWO₄. The
24 light interacting with microscopic structural features in the composite material provides new
25 optical properties, which overcome the possibilities offered by the constituent materials. Here
26 we show remarkable active and passive polarization control of this composite over various
27 wavelength ranges; these properties are based on the crystal orientation of ZnO with respect
28 to biaxiality of ZnWO₄ matrix. In the visible range, polarization dependent polarized
29 luminescence occurs for blue light emitted by ZnO. Moreover, we report on the enhancement
30 of second harmonic generation of the composite with respect to its constituents, due to the
31 phase matching condition. Finally, in the medium infrared spectral region (MIR), the
32 composite behaves as a metamaterial with strong polarization dependence.

35 **1. Introduction**

36

37 Eutectic composites are two-phase crystalline materials, that simultaneously grow from a
38 homogenous liquid phase at a temperature lower than that of its original components. These
39 materials can be formed out of various phases and create different geometrical motifs.^[1-3]
40 Eutectic materials can exhibit a wide range of outstanding properties due to their intrinsic
41 nature, such as: i) highly crystalline component phases with sharp interfaces between them, ii)
42 eutectic structure refinement controllable by the growth rate, from the micro- to the nanoscale,
43 iii) the possibility of engineering the geometric motifs of the precipitates^[4,5] during and after
44 the growth, thus controlling the resulting physical and optical properties, iv) additive
45 properties – properties of eutectic materials borrowed by the ones of their component phases;
46 and v) product properties – novel optical properties that arise from the combination of
47 component phases with a specific structure.

48

49 Recent studies have predicted and demonstrated^[6-8] that eutectic composites can exhibit
50 various interesting optical properties and behave as photonic crystals,^[8] plasmonic
51 metamaterials,^[9,10] THz metamaterials^[11,12] and waveguides,^[13] flexible metamaterials,^[14] or
52 high-operating-temperature ink for writing mesoscale architectures,^[15] just to name some of
53 their interesting behaviors. Therefore, eutectic solidification presents an unrivalled potential
54 for fabricating a broad variety of self-organized optical metamaterials, and, in particular,
55 anisotropic structures.^[16-19] This paves the way towards polarization control in self-organized
56 metamaterials, which makes this inexpensive fabrication competitive with other self-
57 assembling techniques, such as nanosphere lithography for grating polarizers,^[20] colloidal
58 lithography for complex anisotropic nanostructures,^[21,22] wet-spinning nanowire films for
59 visible polarizers,^[23] glancing angle deposition for polarization-sensitive perovskites^[24],
60 nanoporous aluminium for infrared polarizers^[25] etc. In eutectics, furthermore, properly
61 choosing the component phases, the growth parameters and post-growth engineering, can
62 generate the desired optical effects in any spectral regions ranging from visible to THz
63 wavelengths.

64

65 In the present work, we demonstrate and discuss novel and enhanced optical properties of a
66 eutectic composite made from zing tungstate (ZnWO_4) and zinc oxide (ZnO) phases. ZnWO_4
67 is a biaxial, monoclinic crystal that has been used in X-ray and gamma-scintillators,^[26] solid
68 state laser hosts,^[27] optical^[28] and acoustic fibers,^[29] sensors,^[30] and phase-change optical

69 recording media.^[31] Recently, new applications for this material have emerged such as second
70 harmonic generators.^[32] On the other hand, well-crystallized single crystals and
71 nanostructures of ZnO can be used in many areas of science and industry. Thin layers and
72 nanostructures of ZnO have already attracted great interest because of their potential
73 application in LEDs and UV laser technology,^[33,34] as well as in optoelectronic devices,
74 piezoelectric devices,^[35] micro-cavities,^[36] nanoparticles,^[37] second harmonic generators,^[38]
75 UV photodetectors, and acoustic wave devices.^[39]

76

77 Previously, we obtained the ZnO-ZnWO₄ eutectic composite by the micro-pulling-down (μ -
78 PD) method previously.^[18,19] The composite grows with a broken-lamellar structure, with the
79 ZnO phase in the form of perforated nano/microlamellae, ca. 240 nm nanometer in thickness,
80 and hundreds of micrometres in width and length, embedded in the ZnWO₄ matrix. It exhibits
81 strong exciton emission at room temperature, which confirms high quality and crystallinity of
82 the ZnO phase.^[19] Moreover, ZnO-ZnWO₄ eutectic exhibits a narrow-band-transmission at
83 397 nm with the full-width-at-half-maximum of 3 nm, which is a result of the refractive index
84 matching of the two constituent phases at this wavelength range. In addition, this narrow-band
85 transmission remains switchable and tunable with light polarization and temperature.^[18]

86

87 Here we present novel optical properties of the eutectic composite. We first focus on the
88 active properties in the visible spectral range, finding the enhancement of polarized
89 luminescence, and the enhancement of second order nonlinear effects. We further explore
90 passive properties in the medium infrared region (MIR), where the composite behaves as a
91 polarization-dependent metamaterial. These properties result from the combination of bulk
92 properties and the self-organized nano/microstructures, as we experimentally and theoretically
93 demonstrate: they are not observed in ZnO and ZnWO₄ single crystals. Hence the properties
94 of this eutectic could lead to optimized functionalities over broad spectral ranges.

95

96

97 **2. Results and Discussion**

98

99 **2.1. Materials**

100

101 ZnO is a semiconductor ($E_g=3.1-3.3$ eV) that decomposes easily even at lower temperatures,
102 despite its high melting point (1975 °C), which makes it difficult to obtain from a melt. On

103 the other hand, ZnWO_4 is a wide-bandgap dielectric ($E_g=4\text{--}5\text{ eV}$) that is transparent in a broad
104 wavelength range (from $\sim 320\text{ nm}$ to $\sim 10\text{ }\mu\text{m}$). One of the great advantages of the eutectic
105 mixture is that it exhibits lower melting temperature than that of its original components. This
106 is why our composite presents lower melting temperature ($1187\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) than that of ZnO itself,
107 which allows ZnO to grow from the melt without decomposition.^[40]

108

109 The rod of ZnO-ZnWO_4 eutectic has been grown by the micro-pulling down method with the
110 rectangle ($3\times 5\text{ mm}$) crucible shaper. The existence of two constituent phases was confirmed
111 by the powder X-ray diffraction. ZnO crystallizes in a hexagonal system (wurtzite structure)
112 and ZnWO_4 crystallizes in a centrosymmetric monoclinic system.^[32] The growth direction is
113 parallel to a [100] of ZnWO_4 , while directions c [001] and b [010] are always in the plane of a
114 sample.^[19] On the other hand, the c axis of ZnO is in the plane at 90° from the normal to the
115 surface, namely perpendicular to the ZnO lamellae and to the growth direction, as
116 schematically shown in **Figure 1a**. Within one grain, the ZnO lamellae are mostly elongated
117 parallel to the crystal growth direction and ZnWO_4 matrix completely fills up the space
118 between the lamellae and forms sharp interfaces with ZnO , **Figure 1b**. The whole crystal has
119 a rectangle cross-section shape, $5\times 3\text{ mm}$, and it is a 10 cm long. The main crystal (shown in
120 the inset of Figure 1a) was cut in 1 mm thick slices with polished surfaces, thus producing 3
121 similar samples (namely sample A,B and C) for optical characterization.

122

123

124 **Figure 1. ZnO-ZnWO_4 eutectic lamellar heterostructure with ca. 240 nm thick ZnO**
125 **lamellae separated by $2\text{ }\mu\text{m}$, embedded in ZnWO_4 matrix.** (a) Schematic of the sample
126 microstructure and crystallographic orientation of the ZnO lamellae; inset: photograph of the
127 eutectic rod. (b) SEM image of the nanomicrostructure. Eutectic grains can be seen.

128

129 **2.2. Active properties: polarized luminescence in the vis spectral range**

130

131 Self-organized ZnO-ZnWO₄ composites of high quality and low cost were shown to provide
132 strongly polarized and sharp transmission due to the refractive index matching.^[18] Moreover,
133 cathodoluminescence of such samples demonstrated efficient ZnO exciton emission at room
134 temperature.^[19] Inspired by these properties, we first investigated active (emission) properties
135 of ZnO-ZnWO₄ in terms of polarization-resolved excitation and detection. The set-up for
136 transmitted photoluminescence (PL) characterization is shown in **Figure 2a**. Light with the
137 desired wavelength was obtained by a monochromator (Jobin Yvon), illuminated by an arc Xe
138 lamp of 300 W. Photoluminescence spectra were collected with a Minispectrometer Vis/UV
139 using an optical fiber of 200 μm in diameter (Hamamatsu). The sample was positioned on a
140 200 μm thick quartz plate, attached to XYZ stages, in order to facilitate the positioning of the
141 sample with respect to the incident beam and to find the domain of the sample with the
142 highest PL intensity. A long pass filter was used to decrease or eliminate the intensity of the
143 pump, transmitted by the sample. Special care was taken in using the components to minimize
144 the distance between the sample and the optical fiber. The measurements were done in two
145 configurations:

146 A. the linear polarizer was put before the sample (after the monochromator output);

147 B. the linear polarizer was positioned under the sample at a minimum distance.

148 For each configuration, we measured the consequences of the change in the polarizer
149 orientation with respect to lamellae.

150

151 Firstly, we investigated different excitation ranges with respect to the bandgaps of the
152 constituent materials. The sample was excited from the top by unpolarized light and the total
153 emitted intensity was measured for different excitation wavelengths, **Figure 2b**. Note that,
154 since the monochromator emits partially polarized light, the horizontal-to-vertical intensity
155 ratio in our range of wavelengths is around 1.5 (here, the vertical direction at the
156 monochromator's exit corresponds to the direction parallel to the rulings of the diffraction
157 grating). Both materials absorb at 313 nm and strong broadband emission is observed at 480
158 nm. This behavior is due to ZnWO₄ as we previously reported in bulk ZnWO₄ samples:^[32] we
159 observed similar spectra both by exciting ZnWO₄ by an ultraviolet laser and by performing a
160 nonlinear optical experiment which resulted in multiphoton processes. Moreover, a sharp,
161 lower intensity transmission peak appears below 400 nm due to the contribution of the blue
162 exciton emission of ZnO,^[19] and refractive index matching between the two materials.^[18]

163 Although the ultraviolet exciton emission of ZnO peaks at shorter wavelengths (as measured

164 by the cathodoluminescence in ref.^[19]), only part of the tail at 395 nm gets efficiently
 165 transmitted through the sample and arrives at the detector. Increasing the wavelength closer
 166 to the ZnWO₄ bandgap (around 316 nm) decreases the broadband white light emission feature
 167 due to ZnWO₄ while the sharp peak remains. For these short excitation wavelengths, direct
 168 transmission of the excitation beam through the sample is very low (both materials absorb).
 169 Therefore, we did not insert the filter between the sample and the fiber, enabling observation
 170 of PL from ZnWO₄ close to 325 nm. Once the matrix becomes transparent, i.e. for the
 171 excitation at 330 nm, ZnWO₄ poorly emits, as seen from the abrupt decrease of the broadband
 172 emission. Finally, at 360 nm, only the sharp emission from ZnO is present, so we next
 173 investigated its properties in terms of polarization. The last two excitation wavelengths were
 174 filtered in the output, in order to avoid any possible influence of the direct transmission
 175 through the sample.
 176

177
 178 **Figure 2. Photoluminescence of ZnO-ZnWO₄ eutectic composite at the UV-visible range**
 179 **vs. excitation wavelength.** (a) Set-up for the photoluminescence characterization. In
 180 configuration A, the polarizer was positioned in the exit of monochromator to study the
 181 excitation with linearly polarized light. In configuration B, the linear polarizer was positioned
 182 under the sample to study the polarization state of the emitted light. (b) Photoluminescence
 183 spectra of the light transmitted through 1 mm of ZnO-ZnWO₄ for four wavelengths of UV

184 excitation without the use of the linear polarizer; at 313 nm and 316 nm, both materials are in
185 the absorption range so the spectra show broadband generation due to ZnWO₄, and a sharp
186 peak due to ZnO. Crossing the ZnWO₄ bandgap, it poorly emits when excited at 330 nm,
187 while the ZnO peak is preserved. Finally, when the sample was excited at 360 nm, only ZnO
188 absorbed, exhibiting the expected sharp peak under 400 nm. For 330 nm and 360 nm
189 excitation, an additional filter was inserted between the sample and the fiber, to block the
190 directly transmitted excitation beam.

191

192 Anisotropy of the constituent materials allows for index matching, which further leads to
193 strong polarization filtering.^[18] We make use of this property for the polarization-dependent
194 excitation, which controls the emission intensity of the ZnO exciton. We excited the sample
195 from the top with polarized light at 370 nm (configuration A in Figure 2a); this wavelength
196 was chosen as it allows for the assessment of ZnO emission only, giving the maximum PL
197 intensity, while its transmitted part is blocked by the filter in the output.

198

199 The polarization is changed from “parallel” to “orthogonal” with respect to the lamellae,
200 **Figure 3a**. The presented spectra are normalized by taking into account that, due to the
201 monochromator, the “horizontally” polarized light is 1.5 times more intense than the
202 “vertical” one. When electric field is polarized orthogonal to the lamellae (blue line), the
203 overall emission is almost 10 times higher than in the “parallel” case (red line). This is a
204 consequence of a combination factors: the lamellae orientation and ZnWO₄ biaxial
205 anisotropy. Namely, there is a refractive index matching region between ZnO and ZnWO₄
206 growth axis which suppresses the scattering around 395 nm for the “orthogonal” excitation;
207 here, orthogonally polarized light is strongly transmitted, while “parallel” excitation gets
208 extinguished. Beyond this region to shorter wavelengths, ZnO starts to absorb, but the
209 polarization dependence remains the same. We repeated the measurements with the sample
210 rotated by 90° in the horizontal plane; we noted that, in order to observe the PL peak at the
211 sample’s exit, it was necessary to rotate also the polarizer by 90°, as shown in Figure S1. This
212 confirms that the observed effect is governed by the orientation of the incident beam
213 polarization with respect to the lamellae direction.

214

215 Next, we confirmed that the emission polarization follows the discovered phase-matching
216 conditions from ref.^[18]. We now excited the sample with unpolarized light at 370 nm and
217 rotated the linear polarizer in the output (see inset of **Figure 3b**). The transmission of the light

218 generated in the ZnO volume close to the surface follows the phase-matching of the indices at
 219 395 nm, where at the end the polarization of the output beam is perpendicular to the lamellae.
 220 Indeed, the measurements show more than 10-fold contrast ratio between the light emitted to
 221 “perpendicular” with respect to the “parallel” polarization in the output, Figure 3b. The next
 222 step was to measure the transmitted PL signal with both linear polarizers (configurations A+B
 223 in Figure 2b). When the polarizers were crossed, the observed PL signal was negligible, while
 224 it reached maximum intensity when the polarizers were aligned to each other and orthogonal
 225 to the lamellae.
 226

227
 228 **Figure 3. Polarization dependence of the ZnO-ZnWO₄ heterostructure transmitted**
 229 **photoluminescence for excitation at 370 nm.** (a) Photoluminescence spectra when the
 230 excitation is polarized parallel or orthogonal to the lamellae. When electric field is polarized
 231 orthogonal to the lamellae, the overall emission is almost 10 times higher than in the “parallel”
 232 case. (b) Photoluminescence spectra excited at 370 nm by non-polarized light, and the emission
 233 is polarized parallel or orthogonal to the lamellae. There is a remarkable contrast between the
 234 emission polarized perpendicular and parallel to the lamellae, with the first being almost 10
 235 times stronger.

236
 237 To gain a deeper insight into electromagnetic confinement in the composite, we performed 3D
 238 electromagnetic simulations using the high-performance, finite-difference-time-domain
 239 Maxwell’s solver by Lumerical;^[41] details of the simulation set-up are given in Supporting

240 Information, Section 2. We simulated aperiodically positioned ZnO lamellae in ZnWO₄
241 (Figure S2a), following the simulation approach for self-assembled samples from ref.^[42]. The
242 ZnWO₄ refractive index anisotropy is defined by aligning crystallographic axes *c*, *b* and *a*
243 with simulation domain axes *x*, *y* and *z*, respectively (see Table S1). In **Figure 4a-b** we show
244 simulation results for the absorbed, scattered, and transmitted fields when the sample is
245 excited from the top by plane-wave source at 370 nm. We first studied the dependence of the
246 electromagnetic confinement on the excitation polarization, as in the experimental
247 configuration A. The inset of Figure 4 shows the sample being excited from the top by the
248 source field \vec{E}_{in} ; at 370 nm, the part of this field will be absorbed by the ZnO and part will be
249 back-scattered. Figure 4a shows the absorption density ρ_{abs} for the two polarizations of the
250 excitation monitored from the top of the material to a depth of 1 μm . As expected, the
251 absorption takes place only in ZnO, while it manages to reach the deeper ZnO volume when
252 the incident electric field is perpendicular to the lamellae. In the inset, we zoom into the
253 electric intensity confinement for the modes formed in ZnO at 370 nm (see Figure S2b for a
254 complete profile monitor). A stronger and more profound electric field confinement appears
255 for the “orthogonal” excitation; this field, in turn, can excite emission in a larger part of the
256 ZnO material, resulting in the observed enhancement in photoluminescence intensity for the
257 “orthogonal” excitation. This is confirmed also by monitoring of the scattering behind the
258 source (above the sample), Figure 4b. The “parallel” excitation is strongly back-scattered as
259 the lamellae are parallel to the *b*-axis of ZnWO₄, thus leading to a high refractive index
260 mismatch of the constituent materials for this excitation.

261
262 For the case of unpolarized excitation, strongly polarized emission arises from the phase-
263 matching of the light emitted by the material itself at 395 nm. All the excitation of ZnO
264 happens in the part of the sample shown in Figure 3a. Numerous modes supported by the
265 sample at 395 nm travel towards the other end – a distance of ≈ 1 mm. The transmission of
266 such generated light follows the phase-matching of the indices at 395 nm where, at the end,
267 the polarization of the output beam is perpendicular to the lamellae. The highly polarized
268 emission observed in the measurements is further supported by numerical simulations of a
269 randomly-oriented dipole which emits from ZnO to the far-field (Section 2 in Supporting
270 Information) at 395 nm. Only if the dipole is *x*-oriented, the emitted electric field experiences
271 the strongest phase-matching at this wavelength, as we previously noticed in the extraordinary
272 transmission at this wavelength. Therefore, the *x*-polarization gets efficiently transmitted to

273 the far-field, **Figure 4c**. In all other cases, the field gets strongly scattered during its
 274 propagation through the composite (Figure S3).
 275

276
 277 **Figure 4. Simulations of the polarization-dependent excitation and emission; inset: xz-**
 278 **plane with zones where the absorption density and the back-scattered fields are calculated.**
 279 a) 3D distribution of absorption density ρ_{abs} for two cases; for orthogonal excitation, larger
 280 volume of ZnO absorbs light, thus leading to enhanced emission; inset: electric field intensity
 281 distribution in the xz-plane inside the ZnO lamellae. b) Electric field intensity distribution in
 282 the xz-plane above the material and behind the source. While the modes differ in confinement
 283 for the two polarizations inside ZnO, the “parallel” excitation is highly back-scattered. c)
 284 Electric dipole is positioned under the surface and emits at 395 nm; only if the dipole is x-
 285 oriented (upper left) is it transmitted to the far-field, leading to the x-polarized emission (i.e.

286 perpendicular to the lamellae). If the dipole is y -oriented, it strongly emits y -polarized radiation,
287 with the field strongly scattered inside the medium. The z -oriented dipole emits a low intensity
288 of x -polarized radiation (Figure S3).

289

290 **2.3. Active properties: Efficient second harmonic generation (vis-IR spectral range)**

291

292 The demonstrated optical polarization control inside the eutectic ZnO-ZnWO₄ composite,^[18]
293 and the narrow band transmittivity at 400nm, also give rise to efficient optical second
294 harmonic generation (SHG). Here we show that, with the pumping wavelength of 800 nm,
295 SHG is self-optimized when light impinges at the normal incidence with respect to the crystal
296 growth direction. The ZnWO₄ phase of the eutectic composite is a centrosymmetric material
297 (P2/c space group) with some SHG due to local distortion of the crystal and multipolar
298 polarization sources.^[32] The ZnO phase, conversely, with its non-centrosymmetric crystalline
299 structure (P6/3mc space group), might be expected to produce large SHG. However,
300 concerning the excitation direction, in the hexagonal wurtzite phase,^[43] due to symmetry
301 rules, the SHG is not allowed when the fundamental beam direction is parallel to the c -axis,
302 which usually corresponds to normal incidence. Nonetheless, in the eutectic composite, the
303 combination of both of these phases enables different crystallographic orientation of the
304 materials, and the c -axis of ZnO naturally orients in the plane of the sample (perpendicular to
305 the growth direction), ensuring the best condition for phase matching (PM) in SHG when the
306 sample is excited at the normal incidence.

307

308 For a better understanding of the polarization anisotropy of SHG from the ZnO-ZnWO₄
309 eutectic, we pumped the sample at normal incidence with the femtosecond laser beam (pump
310 wavelength 800 nm, pulse duration ~180 fs, average power 70 mW, repetition rate 1 kHz) and
311 we rotated the polarization angle (θ) of the laser from 0° to 180°. The spectra of the
312 polarization-dependent nonlinear signals are presented in the form of 3D charts in **Figure 5a**.
313 For a better view, the maxima of SHG measured signals (~400 nm) are plotted as a function
314 of polarization angle of the input beam (**Figure 5b**). The observed polarization dependence is
315 related to the symmetry of the susceptibility tensor of the ZnO hexagonal crystal structure and
316 the preferred a -axis orientation of the ZnO lamellae in the eutectic material. Namely, even
317 though there is a much lower volume contribution of this material with respect to the
318 centrosymmetric ZnWO₄ matrix, ZnO has been known for highly efficient SHG behavior.<sup>[43-
319 45]</sup> As previously mentioned, since the c -axis of ZnO is oriented perpendicularly to ZnO

320 lamellae and lies within the plane of the sample, such a configuration can give efficient SHG
321 signal even at normal incidence. As a further confirmation, the theoretical fit in Figure 5b also
322 corroborates this experimental polarization dependence of SHG signal for ZnO-ZnWO₄. The
323 ZnO crystal structure, due to Kleinman's symmetry rules, presents the nonvanishing second
324 order susceptibility tensor elements $d_{15}=d_{24}=d_{31}=d_{32}$, and d_{33} . This tensor must be rotated by
325 90° to account for the particular in-plane orientation of *c*-axis. Using such a rotated tensor, we
326 performed the fitting procedure by setting $d_{15}=1$ and taking d_{33} as the only fitting parameter;
327 here, the SHG intensity is given as $W_{2\omega} \sim |d_{\text{eff}}|^2$, where d_{eff} is the effective nonlinear
328 coefficient that takes into account the rotated nonlinear optical tensor, as well as the incidence
329 angle and polarization of the input and SHG beams (more details can be found in the
330 Supporting Information, Section 3). From the experimental results, a fitted value of $d_{33}=-$
331 0.655 was obtained. Although this value is lower with respect to the value expected for a
332 highly-crystalline ZnO phase in a single ideal lamella domain, it is consistent with the
333 hypothesis that the overall SHG signal is composed of an averaged contribution from several
334 grains with different orientations of the lamellae and, consequently, with different orientation
335 of the *c*-axis in the plane of the sample (as depicted in the inset of Figure 5b).

336

337 To compare the magnitude of the generated signal, we used the same laser to measure SHG
338 from a commercial beta barium borate (BBO) crystal and from the ZnWO₄ bulk slab used in
339 ref.^[32] We take into account the different impedance mismatch between the vacuum (where
340 the input beam travels) and the respective interfaces of the three aforementioned slabs (details
341 are given in Section 3 of Supporting Information). In **Figure 5c**, we show the normalized
342 power profiles of the three samples (BBO, ZnWO₄, and ZnO-ZnWO₄ eutectic crystal) with
343 respect to the wavelength λ , where the maximum SHG signal of BBO is fixed at 1. As
344 expected, the BBO crystal exhibits the highest SHG efficiency, while bulk ZnWO₄ delivers
345 only very weak SHG signal which is slightly above 0.5% of the BBO maximum. Finally,
346 ZnO-ZnWO₄ eutectic crystal reaches SHG as high as 20% of the maximum BBO power at
347 $\lambda \approx 400$ nm, even though it comes from a self-organized structure without the use of time-
348 consuming and expensive synthesis procedure required to grow BBO single crystals. In terms
349 of efficiency of the nonlinear optical process, the obtained results are very promising,
350 considering the low cost and fast growth procedure to obtain the eutectic ZnO-ZnWO₄ crystal
351 with respect to the growth procedure that is necessary for the BBO. Moreover, further study
352 and optimization of the parameters will likely lead to ZnO-ZnWO₄ eutectic crystals with
353 larger or even single crystalline domains with mono-oriented lamellae. In turn, this should

354 lead to a SHG efficiency comparable with that of a BBO crystal since pure ZnO efficiency^[43]
355 can reach values comparable with that of BBO.^[46]

356

357 This enhancement of SHG from ZnO-ZnWO₄ eutectic composite can be attributed to the
358 presence of *a*-axis oriented ZnO lamellae. It is well known the ZnO hexagonal lattice shows
359 strong tendency to crystalize with *c*-axis orientation; therefore such oriented films and
360 nanostructures can be easily produced.^[47] Consequently, ZnO with *a*-axis orientation has
361 seldom been investigated.^[48] ZnO with this particular orientation displays strong increase in
362 conversion efficiency with respect to *c*-axis oriented ZnO. The eutectic growth promotes the
363 *a*-axis orientation in ZnO, so higher efficiencies were expected at the normal incidence and
364 now are experimentally confirmed. Additionally, in systems consisting of multiple layers,
365 SHG contributions from the surface and interface cannot be excluded. As a result of the flat
366 and atomically smooth ZnO-ZnWO₄ interface,^[19] symmetry breaking is expected for each
367 boundary between ZnO and ZnWO₄, thus further raising the efficiency of SHG in this eutectic
368 material.

369

370 In order to conduct an additional investigation on the SHG emission from the ZnO-ZnWO₄
371 eutectic, angle dependent studies of the nonlinear effects were performed, as shown in **Figure**
372 **5d**. The angle dependence of SHG was measured by replacing the spectrophotometer with a
373 photomultiplier and adding a vertical polarizer before the detector. The pump at 800 nm was
374 set to either \hat{p} or \hat{s} polarization state, corresponding to 0° and 90° in Figure 5b, where the
375 maximum SHG signal was recorded. A 40 nm passband filter centered at approximately 400
376 nm ensures that only the SHG signal is measured. The sample is placed on the rotation stage
377 in the range of -40° to +40°. The highest SHG intensity was recorded at almost normal
378 incidence; however, we noted additional two peaks of lower intensity, at around ±30° with
379 respect to the incident beam, Figure 5d. This means that the alignment of ZnO lamellae
380 differs in each eutectic grain. The two small SHG peaks at angle of incidence of ±30° may
381 correspond to very small fraction of ZnO *c*-axis oriented out of the plane of the sample.

382

383

384 **Figure 5. Second harmonic generation at the normal to the incidence condition in the**

385 **broken-lamellar ZnO-ZnWO₄ eutectic composite.** (a) Polarization dependence of spectral

386 SHG. (b) Experimental polarization dependence of SHG at 400 nm (dark blue), and theoretical

387 model (light grey). The inset displays a multigrain character of the eutectic that provides the

388 condition for the SHG, regardless of the input polarization angles. (c) Comparison of relative

389 spectral intensity of SHG signal at the normal incidence for BBO, ZnWO₄ and ZnO-ZnWO₄.

390 (d) SHG intensity from the eutectic as a function of the incident angle of the fundamental beam.

391

392 **2.4. Passive properties: MIR metamaterial with strong polarization management**

393

394 In a previous work, we reported a strong and narrowband polarization sensitive filtering

395 behavior from eutectic ZnWO₄/ZnO structures in the visible/UV range.^[18] High transmission

396 was obtained at a specific wavelength and polarization when the refractive indices of the two

397 constituents matched and the composite medium appeared homogenous. In every other

398 condition, strong scattering losses drastically reduced transmission. Here we investigate

399 excitation wavelengths corresponding to the IR atmospheric window between 8 and 14 μm
400 and show that a similar behavior can be achieved in reflection mode with the same structures.
401 In this wavelength range, the eutectic structure behaves as a self-assembled metamaterial
402 containing both ZnO and ZnWO₄ domains much smaller than the exciting wavelengths. Thus,
403 the physical mechanisms triggering the strong infrared anisotropic response are completely
404 different with respect to the previously described phenomena in the visible range.

405
406 Acting as natural, self-assembled, polarizing filters the investigated eutectic composites
407 display strong potentialities for the development of photonics components in the IR. In the
408 seek for a complete IR photonic platform, miniaturization and integration of optical elements
409 with the chip-scale platforms using facile fabrication techniques^[25,49] is highly desired.
410 Conventional IR polarizers are nowadays designed using state of the art holographic
411 techniques^[50] onto IR transparent support (CaF₂, ZnSe, BaF₂) with typical transmission losses
412 of about 30%. Similarly, polarization rotators have been theoretically designed using artificial
413 metasurfaces^[51] or Van der Waals materials.^[52] Long wavelengths polarizing elements are
414 achieved using a combination of two parallel polarizers and by tilting the plates with respect
415 to each other.^[53] So far, control and manipulation of light polarization in the atmospheric
416 window by low cost and compact devices is still an unreached goal in the development of a
417 photonic platform for sensing of biomolecules and harmful/explosive substances as well as
418 for thermal imaging and diagnostics.

419
420 In order to analyze this behavior, we first introduce the IR optical properties of bulk ZnWO₄.
421 According to IR reflectance spectra^[54] and Raman spectroscopy investigations^[55], ZnWO₄ has
422 two Reststrahlen bands (RB) arising from material's optical phonons response. We now focus
423 our attention on the band between 880cm⁻¹ and 910 cm⁻¹ (approx. 11 μm wavelength),
424 corresponding to the bending and stretching vibrations of the Zn-W-O bond; and on the band
425 between 705-756 cm⁻¹ (centered at 13.5 μm) corresponding to the bending and stretching
426 vibrations of the W-O bond. As a first step we performed measurements of reflection spectra
427 as a function of the input linear polarization of bulk ZnWO₄ obtained with the same micro-
428 pulling method used for the eutectic structures and described in the previous section.
429 Reflection spectra have been collected using a Bruker FTIR-Hyperion microscope and are
430 reported in **Figure 6a**. The obtained measurements data were related to a gold reference
431 mirror, which has a reflectance nearly independent on wavelength and was employed to
432 obtain the sample reflectance. The two previously mentioned RBs are clearly shown as high

433 reflection bands. However, bulk ZnWO_4 spectra are almost polarization insensitive as Figure
434 6a displays only a slight variation as a function of the polarization angle of the incident beam,
435 which is related to the crystal natural anisotropy.

436

437 A completely different scenario is reported when eutectic ZnO-ZnWO_4 structures are
438 considered. We show in **Figures 6b-d** a strong modulation of the reflection bands as a
439 function of the incident light linear polarization for three samples (labelled, as a reference,
440 sample A, B and C) obtained taking three different slices of the same crystal shown in Figure
441 1, with a thickness of 1 mm. Because of the self-assembled nature of the structure, we expect
442 a similar (not identical) behavior for the three samples related to the average filling factor and
443 the partial order of the eutectic structure. The reduction of the reflected signal can be directly
444 related to the coupling of the incident light to surface phonon polaritons (SPhP) at the
445 interfaces between ZnWO_4 and ZnO . According to the SPhP theory, a planar interface
446 between two isotropic media having opposite signs of dielectric permittivities supports
447 surface waves with the electric field having a nonzero component along the direction normal
448 to the interface. Indeed, while the dielectric constant of ZnWO_4 in the RB is negative, the
449 dielectric constant of ZnO in this range is positive^[56] making possible the excitation of surface
450 waves at every interface. This is in agreement with the experimental reduction of reflectance
451 reported when the electric field is polarized perpendicularly to lamellae direction in the 880-
452 910 cm^{-1} band.

453

454 The coupling efficiency between the incident light and surface modes is affected by several
455 geometrical parameters, including the distance between ZnO lamellae; their thicknesses; and,
456 most importantly, the polarization direction of incident light with respect to lamellae
457 orientation. Indeed, different conditions of minimum and maximum reflectance as a function
458 of the polarization angle of incident light for the three samples refer to different orientations
459 of the in lamellae the laboratory frame. However, the argument employed to explain the
460 modulation of reflectance in the 880-910 cm^{-1} band cannot be used to explain the behavior of
461 reflectance in the other band. Indeed, experimental results also show that while the condition
462 of minimum (maximum) reflectance for the 880-910 cm^{-1} band is achieved for orthogonal
463 polarizations, perpendicular (parallel) to the directions of the lamellae, the other band seems
464 to be less affected by the polarization and conditions for maximum and minimum reflectance
465 are reversed.

466

467

468 **Figure 6. Experimental reflectance spectra as a function of the frequency and the incident**
 469 **field polarization angle. (a) Bulk ZnWO₄; (b) Sample A; (c) Sample B and (d) Sample C.**

470

471 This could be ascribed to anisotropy of both the constituent media. Indeed, at the interfaces
 472 between anisotropic media it is possible to excite a wide variety of surface waves i.e.
 473 Dyakonov waves, hyperbolic surface polaritons and other recently reported exotic surface
 474 waves.^[57] Furthermore, other features such as geometrical and/or material parameters are also
 475 expected to affect the different behavior of the two RBs. In order to provide a deeper
 476 interpretation of the phenomenon by numerical simulations, the dielectric permittivity tensor
 477 of both ZnO and ZnWO₄ are needed. However, to the best of our knowledge a complete
 478 characterization of bulk, single crystal, ZnWO₄ by spectroscopic ellipsometry has never been
 479 performed in this wavelength range; thus this surely deserves further investigation.

480

481 The difference among the spectra for the three samples is clearly noticeable in Figure 6b-d as
 482 is typical for the self-assembling process. Nevertheless, the versatile and easy fabrication
 483 process allows the realization of structures with interesting potential applications as tunable

484 polarization-sensitive mirrors in a range between 750 and 900 cm^{-1} . In order to highlight this
485 feature, we report in **Figure 7** the reflectance as a function of the incident field polarization
486 angle for different frequencies for sample A (blue squares), B (red circles) and C (black
487 triangles). Sample A has the best performance at 838 cm^{-1} (Figure 7d, reflectance ranging
488 from 0.97 to 0.14), however sample B and sample C have similar performances even if they
489 work on a narrower band. For example, the reflectance value of sample C at 869 cm^{-1} is
490 strongly modulated between 0.75 and 0.14 (Figure 7e). Although not perfectly predictable by
491 initial design, due to the self-assembling procedure, the polarizing features in the atmospheric
492 IR window between 8 and 14 μm can be found in every sample and this peculiar property
493 could be exploited for the future realization of low cost IR polarizing elements.
494

495

496 **Figure 7. Experimental reflection vs. the incident field polarization angle of sample A**
 497 **(blue squares), sample B (red circles) and sample C (black triangles) for different**
 498 **frequencies in the range between 745 cm^{-1} and 900 cm^{-1} . a) 745 cm^{-1} ; b) 776 cm^{-1} ; c) 807**
 499 **cm^{-1} ; d) 838 cm^{-1} ; e) 869 cm^{-1} ; f) 900 cm^{-1} .**

500

501

502 **Conclusions**

503

504 In summary, we have performed a detailed investigation of polarization properties of ZnO-
505 ZnWO₄ eutectic composite grown by μ -PD. We investigated photoluminescence, SHG and
506 highly efficient polarization control in the visible and MIR range. Firstly, specific
507 arrangements of the a-axis oriented ZnO lamellae were shown to produce photoluminescence
508 strongly dependent on the excitation polarization; moreover, the emitted light from the ZnO
509 lamellae was also polarized perpendicular to the lamellae, due to refractive index matching
510 condition. Secondly, phase matching in ZnWO₄ within the ZnO-ZnWO₄ eutectic was shown
511 to produce enhanced SHG. Moreover, the multigrain character of the eutectic composite
512 provides the necessary condition for the SHG, regardless of the input polarization angle. This
513 resembles nature's way of making omnidirectional materials: for example, in *Parides sesostris*
514 butterfly adjacent but differently oriented domains of an identical three-dimensional structure
515 provide a three-dimensional photonic crystal exhibiting green color which is independent of
516 the viewing angle.^[58] This robust performance of the ZnO-ZnWO₄ composite at normal
517 incidence is obtained by a large scale and cost-effective fabrication method which makes this
518 material very attractive for applications, as an alternative to sizeable - and hence expensive -
519 nonlinear single crystals. Finally, we showed remarkable polarization properties for longer
520 MIR wavelengths where this self-assembled composite acts as a metamaterial. We believe
521 that the engineering of this material can be considered for novel optical and MIR components.

522

523 **Experimental Section/Methods**

524

525 *I. Sample fabrication and structure characterization:*

526

527 Rods of ZnO-ZnWO₄ eutectic composites a few centimeters in length and a rectangle cross-
528 section with 5x3 mm shape were successfully grown at the Łukasiewicz Research Network –
529 Institute of Microelectronics and Photonics.

530 In order to obtain the ZnO-ZnWO₄ eutectic system, first the raw materials for the micro-
531 pulling down method^[59] were prepared by mixing high-purity ZnO (Alfa Aesar; 99.999%)
532 and WO₃ (Alfa Aesar; 99.99%) powders at a fixed composition of 65 mol.% ZnO and 35
533 mol.% WO₃ in an agate mortar with 2-propanol. The obtained mixture was dried in air at
534 350 °C for 2 h to eliminate volatile impurities. After drying, the material was placed in the
535 metallic crucible and heated. The material was then transferred to the μ -PD apparatus for
536 crystal growth, where it was seed-grown with a <001> strontium-lanthanum gallate

537 (SrLaGaO₄) single crystal. The eutectic rods were obtained from an iridium crucible in a
538 nitrogen atmosphere with a 0.2 mm/min pulling rate. To decrease the radial temperature
539 gradient, an active iridium after heater and two insulating zirconium dioxide (ZrO₂) and
540 aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) ceramics were used. The whole process was controlled manually by
541 changing the pulling rate and output power of the power generator at the initial stage of
542 growth and the growth processes were monitored by a CCD camera. Both-side polished
543 samples cut from the original ZnO-ZnWO₄ rod were used for further characterization.

544

545 Microstructure characterization was carried out with Carl Zeiss Scanning Electron
546 Microscope (SEM) Auriga® CrossBeam® Workstation with an Energy Dispersive
547 Spectroscopy detector (EDS) for chemical composition analysis.

548

549 *II. Experimental details for SHG measurements:*

550

551 SHG measurements were carried out at the Sapienza University of Rome by means of a
552 collinear scheme working in transmission. The input light source was a pulsed Ti:sapphire
553 laser at ~800 nm (central wavelength 795 nm, bandwidth 11 nm, pulse duration 180 fs,
554 repetition rate 1 kHz, average power 70 mW). The input beam was \hat{p} -polarized and controlled
555 by rotating $\lambda/2$ plate. The sample was placed onto a motorized stage, allowing the variation of
556 the sample rotation angle from -40° to $+40^\circ$. The outgoing light was filtered by a short pass
557 filter in order to remove the strong pump light and then sent to a fiber spectrometer. In the
558 case of angular dependence, the spectrometer was replaced by a photomultiplier preceded by
559 a polarizer (analyzer) that can be set for either \hat{p} or \hat{s} polarization. The spectral selectivity of
560 the photomultiplier was ensured by a 40 nm bandpass filter centered at 400 nm. For
561 transmission measurements, a BBO crystal was added to the set-up before the half waveplate
562 to generate SH of 400 nm.

563

564 *III. FTIR characterization:*

565

566 IR reflectance measurements have been performed on a Bruker FTIR-Hyperion microscope at
567 the INFN-LNF Dafne-Light facility in Frascati, Italy. The IR source was a glow-bar while the
568 detector was a liquid nitrogen-cooled mercury–cadmium–telluride photo-voltaic element. A
569 total of 64 interferograms were acquired for each measurements, with a spectral resolution of
570 2 cm^{-1} . Spectra have been collected at different polarization orientations of incident light

571 ranging from 0° to 180° with steps of 22.5°. For all the investigated samples we used knife
572 edge apertures to select a surface area of 200x200 μm² exhibiting a good distribution of
573 lamellae in terms of periodicity and uniform thickness. This way it has been possible to find a
574 correspondence between polarization orientation of incident light and lamellae direction.

575

576

577 **Supporting Information**

578 Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

579

580 **Acknowledgements**

581 The authors thank the ENSEMBLE³ Project carried within the Teaming for Excellence
582 Horizon 2020 programme of the European Commission (GA No. 857543), and the
583 International Research Agendas Programme (MAB/2020/14) of the Foundation for Polish
584 Science co-financed by the European Union under the European Regional Development Fund
585 and Teaming Horizon 2020 programme of the European Commission. . The authors thank
586 also the TEAM/2016-3/29 Grant within the TEAM programme of the Foundation for Polish
587 Science co-financed by the European Union under the European Regional Development Fund
588 and the HARMONIA Project (2013/10/M/ST5/00650) from the National Science Centre, for
589 support of this work. Authors would also like to thank Mariangela Cestelli Guidi and Martina
590 Romani at INFN-LNF Dafne-Light for their hospitality and support with the FTIR
591 microscopy. A.B. acknowledges LASAFEM Sapienza Università di Roma Infrastructure
592 Project Prot. n. MA31715C8215A268.

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